

SOME CONSIDERATIONS ON THE PREVENTION INSPECTOR'S WORK WITH INDIVIDUALS EXHIBITING ANTISOCIAL BEHAVIOR

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Abstract: This article examines the prevention inspector's work with individuals exhibiting antisocial behavior, including its concept, main directions, specific features, organizational and legal foundations, and best practices from foreign countries in this area. It analyzes existing problems in the prevention inspector's activities when working with individuals exhibiting antisocial behavior and develops proposals and recommendations for their solutions.

Keywords: The concept of prevention inspector's work with individuals exhibiting antisocial behavior, organizational and legal foundations of prevention inspector's work with individuals exhibiting antisocial behavior.

Today, the Republic of Uzbekistan is implementing large-scale reforms aimed at protecting the rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests of individuals. Ensuring the protection of fundamental human rights and freedoms is an integral characteristic of any state that has chosen the path of building a civil society. Its implementation is aimed at safeguarding the relationship between individuals and the state and its bodies in the sphere of law and order, as well as in the fight against crime, protecting them from interference in vital areas of human life. Additionally, the state and law enforcement agencies are tasked with guaranteeing the rights and freedoms of individuals and citizens through the means and methods at their disposal. Guided by the slogan of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev Miromonovich, "We will build a new Uzbekistan together with our wise and hardworking people," law enforcement agencies are responsibly fulfilling the aforementioned tasks.

One of the main issues in legal psychology is, first and foremost, the identification of internal personal conditions that the motivational sphere of the individual can create for this individual a criminogenic situation in interaction with certain factors in the external environment. Sometimes certain forms of negative behavior become a single interest, detached from the conditions associated with the individual's initial needs. Plots, gossip, slander, causing inconvenience to others, and scandals often manifest themselves as a distorted form of self-determination and the manifestation of social activity. Even crimes that seem absurd at first glance have a certain meaning, personal significance for the criminal. Any crime is specifically linked to the needs, interests, or views of a criminal. A person's low level of knowledge, underdeveloped consciousness, inability to understand the consequences of their actions, inability to control themselves, that is, antisocial behavior leads a person to commit an offense. As a result, such people easily commit crimes against the individual in the pursuit of their selfish goals, i.e., assaults against human life and health, such as murder, grievous bodily harm, torture, without thinking about it. As a result of the lack of qualities

such as compassion and pity, people of this category commit crimes dangerous to human life and health with barbarism as a result of spiritual poverty.

According to scientific data, the psychological content and essence of antisocial behavior also lie in the interests of the individual. Interests determine a person's behavior and its content and ensure their activity in achieving their goals.

Therefore, it can be said that antisocial interests participate in the emergence of behavioral deviations in children and adolescents and serve as a specific internal force and direction for its realization. In other words, antisocial interests manifest themselves as an internal force that influences the emergence of behavioral deviations, influencing the emergence of behavioral deviations and serving their realization. In our study (the socio-psychological questionnaire "Study of the Commitment of Antisocial Behavior by Minors as a Result of Voluntary or Other Influences," developed by F.K. Iskanzhanova for her doctoral dissertation on the topic "Socio-psychological Problems of Behavioral Deviation in Minors"), a socio-psychological questionnaire developed to study the influence of antisocial behavior and interests on the occurrence of behavioral deviations in children and adolescents was used. According to the survey results, out of 93 respondents studied, 56.48% of antisocial behavior was committed by children and adolescents at their own discretion, 10.64% as a result of the influence of peers or others, 8.24% as a result of the influence of adults, 4.39% as a result of the influence of parents and relatives, and 11.84% as a result of the influence of previously convicted criminals. The survey questions addressed to the respondents were as follows:

1. Do you believe that you committed your illegal act voluntarily? ("Yes" or "No.")
2. Do you believe that your friends or peers have an influence on the implementation of illegal behavior? ("Yes" or "No.")
3. Do you think there is influence from older neighbors or someone else in your unlawful behavior? ("Yes" or "No.")
4. Do you think that your parents and loved ones have an influence on the implementation of illegal behavior? ("Yes" or "No.")
5. Are there any of your acquaintances who have been convicted? ("Yes" or "No.")
6. Do you think that your previously convicted acquaintances influenced you to commit an illegal act? ("Yes" or "No.").

The survey results revealed that children and adolescents did not explicitly acknowledge the role of external influences in committing antisocial behavior. Therefore, we would like to emphasize that when analyzing whether antisocial acts committed by minors were voluntary or influenced by others, using information from initiated procedural documents has yielded good results. According to statistical data, a quarter of the antisocial behavior committed by children and adolescents in our republic occurred with the participation or influence of adults.

The relevance of the topic in preventing offenses and crimes in our society today is linked to the following:

First, the insufficient capacity of prevention inspectors, established as a result of reforms, to work with individuals exhibiting antisocial behavior;

Second, the presence of contradictions and problems in the legal framework supporting the activities of crime prevention departments (divisions); Third, the existence of issues in organizing, coordinating, and legally regulating the cooperation between crime

prevention departments (divisions) and other internal affairs units and public structures, as well as in implementing such cooperation;

Fourth, the need to study and implement best practices in this area;

Fifth, the prevalence of various conditions enabling the cultivation of prohibited crops, which crime prevention departments must address;

Sixth, the presence of problems in providing organizational and tactical support for the activities of crime prevention departments, and so on.

Additionally, it is planned to introduce effective criteria for evaluating the performance of prevention inspectors. The following tasks are outlined in developing these criteria:

First, considering public opinion, citizens' satisfaction with the results of their activities, and the level of cooperation with the population;

Second, establishing a qualitatively new framework for the activities of crime prevention units at the national, regional, and local levels, clearly defining and delimiting their main tasks, functions, and responsibilities, while preventing the imposition of non-specific functions on prevention inspectors;

Third, organizing preventive work in close cooperation with the population, citizens' self-government bodies, and other civil society institutions, aiming this work primarily at ensuring early prevention of offenses, raising legal awareness in society, and instilling in citizens respect for the law and intolerance towards any manifestation of law violations;

Fourth, tasks such as widespread promotion of modern information and communication technologies in this sphere, enhancing the knowledge and professional training of prevention inspectors, creating decent working conditions for them, providing them with official accommodation in their assigned territories, and introducing mechanisms for material incentives based on the effectiveness of their assigned tasks.

The interconnected activities of preventive inspectors with individuals with antisocial behavior include the following: theoretical foundations, consisting of the doctrines of the preventive inspector's activities with individuals with antisocial behavior; institutional foundations, consisting of subjects ensuring the activities of the preventive inspector with individuals with antisocial behavior; legal foundations, consisting of normative legal acts defining and regulating the activities of preventive inspectors with individuals with antisocial behavior; organizational and tactical foundations, consisting of the forms and methods

Like the roots of any tree, antisocial behavior has its origins, its starting point, which is formed in a person from childhood, taking the example of his parents and family from those around him, and growing up, it shapes his attitude towards life and people depending on the upbringing he receives. In Uzbekistan, the mahalla is viewed as a small part of the social environment. In our country, the mahalla is viewed as the most important part of our lives, it is not for nothing that seven mahallas are called parents for one child, but the individual way of influencing people with antisocial behavior may not help, but under the influence of many, the intended goal can be achieved.

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